

NEWSLETTER

ISSUE 3, FEBRUARY 2024

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1. BIOSYSMO PROGRESS

IDENER

During the first 18 months of the project, IDENER has made significant progress in data collection and integration, completing the first iteration of data gathering from diverse online repositories. This effort has led to the creation of an integrated, cross-referenced database, a central hub for diverse information associated with the degradation pathways of xenobiotics, chemical compounds of environmental significance. The database includes curated data on chemical compounds, their roles in biodegradation pathways, reactions, and the enzymes and microorganisms involved. Developed using Structured Query Language (SQL), this database not only serves as a reliable repository but also provides a foundation for advanced querying, analysis, and visualization of data, marking a significant step forward in understanding and managing these complex chemical interactions.

A notable aspect of this part of the project is the focus on enzymes and proteins involved in these reactions. IDENER has downloaded their protein sequences, wherever available, and clustered them based on both their amino acid compositions and functional characteristics. From these clusters, Hidden Markov Models (HMM) representative of each protein group have been developed. These models are being employed in inferring the presence of these proteins in genomes associated with the different spaces included in BIOSYSMO. IDENER has also searched for proteins associated with metal resistance mechanism for fungi and bacteria. With all these sequences, it has created a dataset that is being used to try to identify the presence or absence of these types of mechanisms in the genomes and organisms already offered by the partners, especially CIIMAR, JSI and UBFC.

IDENER has already initiated the genome-scale reconstructions for selected microorganisms to be implemented in the BIOSYSMO biosystems for their bioremediation and biodegradation activities. Amongst these are *Pseudomonas putida*, which will undergo genetic modification to contain the lindane degradation pathway. For this task, IDENER will support ICL by performing in-silico simulations of this pathway within the genome-scale metabolic model of *P. putida* to make useful predictions. UBFC selected six fungal strains based on their initial characterization of metal resistance and plant-growth promoting traits of all the isolates at Site 10. IDENER has already generated the preliminary models for these strains to further assist their screening tests at a genomic level. IDENER has identified the most relevant targets from the pollutants characterized on the BIOSYSMO sites by the partners for the definition and initiation of different site-oriented and compound-oriented predictive toxicity models. Considering the large complexity and diversity of metallic and organic compounds identified in the sites, IDENER has defined different approaches that involve single-compound and mixture models, together with the exploitation of tools such as the QSAR Toolbox. Together with UBU and LEITAT common targets have been defined to give a holistic evaluation of the ecotoxicological assessment.

1. BIOSYSMO PROGRESS

UBU

During this period, UBU, together with the contributions of LEITAT and IDENER, has worked on the definition of the in vitro (eco)toxicological approaches for the selected polluted soil, sediment and water samples. In order to evaluate the efficacy in terms of eco(toxicology) of the BIOSYSMO technologies, the information provided by the partners on the physicochemical characteristics of the samples has been determinant to select the most appropriate methodologies and to guarantee the quality of the assays. First (eco)toxicological tests are being performed using 2D and 3D human lung cells, yeast and soil model bacteria.

Additionally, UBU has been working during these 18 months in different activities related with the technology water phytoremediation and soil bioremediation. To improve water remediation technologies for metal removal, UBU has been investigated the capacity of plant *Phragmites australis* to act as hyperaccumulator of metals and how the removal efficiency can be improved by Plant Growth-Promoting Rhizobacteria (PGPRs) isolated from polluted environments. Due to the limited knowledge about various aspects of the plant, several experiments have been conducted to select in vitro growth methods, seed disinfection protocols for subsequent inoculation exclusively with the desired PGPR, and different bacterial inoculation methods. Additionally, several tests were conducted on bacteria isolated from environments contaminated with heavy metals to determine if they exhibited PGPR traits and at least 13 of them yielded positive results for at least one of the tests. Moreover, the expression of genes related to metal detoxification

(heavy metal transporters, metallothionein....) and antioxidant activity is also being studied to understand the plant's response to the presence of heavy metals. This progress is oriented to enhance the plant-microorganisms for improved phytoremediation for metal removal and its further integration with bioelectrochemical systems reactors.

For soil bioremediation technologies for organic removal, UBU will use two soils, one contaminated with PAH (and metals) and one contaminated with Lindane. During 2023, UBU ended the sampling of the Lindane Site and isolation of microorganisms for these polluted sites are in progress.

1. BIOSYSMO PROGRESS

JSI

Over the last 18 months, JSI partner has been actively engaged in various activities within the BIOSYSMO project. They successfully isolated micro-communities using the iACME method from multiple sample sites. Additionally, JSI researchers visited LEITAT for training in BES methods, while JSI conducted tests on polyelectrolytes for immobilization in BES systems. In Task 3.2, in collaboration with LEITAT, JSI researchers have been

refining an experimental plan to study microorganism niches involved in pollutant degradation. They have also prepared chambers for building and testing electrogenic biofilms and explored the use of vaterite particles for cell attachment in carrier construction. Furthermore, they have been developing a method to indicate electrogenic strains using vanadate. These activities reflect JSI's dedication to advancing bioremediation technologies within the project.

LEITAT

LEITAT

Aiming to develop new techniques for the functional growth of electroactive biofilms, Leitrat and JSI have been working together. A week-long training on Bio electrochemical Systems operation was carried out at Leitrat facilities. During the training, the electrochemical operation of two different strategies was defined. The first one is based on electrode potential modulation, and Leitrat has been using it to isolate electroactive bacteria from polluted groundwater to support pollutant degradation in various BES reactor types. Three different reactors have been designed for polluted groundwater treatment to remove heavy metals, hydrocarbons (TPHs and BTEX), and chlorinated ethenes. A fourth reactor is under development, aiming to integrate phytoremediation in Microcosms Floating Systems (MFS)

and electro-bioremediation in BES.

Leitrat has defined the in vivo ecotoxicological evaluation strategy for the selected samples. Common targets have been defined to provide a holistic evaluation of the entire ecotoxicological assessment, in collaboration with UBU and IDENER. The shipment of the already collected samples was coordinated between Leitrat, UBU, TAUW, and UBFC to maintain the quality of the samples for the ecotoxicological evaluation. Leitrat has initiated the in vivo ecotoxicological characterization of the received samples, adapting the methodologies selected in agreement with UBU and IDENER to avoid erroneous evaluation of the results due to the high conductivity values of some samples.

1. BIOSYSMO PROGRESS

UBFC

UBFC had made significant contribution to WP1 by collecting, characterizing and sharing the polluted samples from 3 sites. The sampling campaigns were fully described in site factsheet. Site 1 It is a soil site contaminated with metals and PAHs and is being used by UBFC and UPM for phytoremediation. UBFC has determined metal content and CNRS analyzed a wide range of pesticides. Site 2 is a soil contaminated with Hg and chlorinated ethenes. UBFC and JSI analyzed metals and metalloids. UBFC also analyzed chlorinated ethenes. JSI also analyzed the two most important Hg species, Hg and methyl-Hg, and carried out a screening of emerging contaminants. Site 3 is a soil contaminated with metals, TPHs and PAHs. UBFC has determined metal content. Profile of contamination (total EPHs and 16 PAH-EPA) has been analyzed. UBFC conducted the enrichment and isolation of microorganisms, including bacteria and fungi, from these polluted samples. Upon this characterization, the most promising isolates were used to establish a collection of bacterial and fungal isolates by using conventional enrichment and isolation approaches in the presence of contaminants. Molecular identification (16S rRNA or ITS) was performed on isolated

microbes and consortia. The large number of microbial isolates obtained facilitates the identification of suitable strains for the removal of target pollutants but also poses a challenge for the selection of the most suitable strains for deeper characterized by WGS approaches, as it will not be feasible to analyze the entire collection of isolates. However, we have narrow down the selection by closely interacting with task 3.1, where the isolates have been characterized for their resistance to the metals found on the site (zinc, lead and cadmium), their ability to promote plant growth (production of growth regulators, increased nutrient collection, etc.) and to degrade organic pollutants. The known fungal plant endophytes (e.g., *Beauveria* sp., *Exophiala*, *Samsoniella*) have been further tested for their plant growth promoting (PGP) traits in WP3. Results from these initial screening tests allow us to decide which microbial strains should be retained for further characterization in WP2 and WP3. Selected consortia are further analyzed with metagenomic WGS to determine dependencies between strains and potentially coupled metabolic pathways assisting in pollutant degradation coupled with in silico determination in WP2.

1. BIOSYSMO PROGRESS

BSY

Blue Synergy conducted a comprehensive literature review on various aspects related to soil remediation. This review included the assessment of life cycle analysis (LCA) for soil remediation processes, examining the challenges encountered in the remediation of contaminated sites. Another focus was on exploring bio-electrochemical solutions for soil and water remediation through an extensive literature review. The project also conducted a literature review on techno-economic assessments of soil remediation processes, identifying challenges in this area.

Additionally, a literature review was carried out to analyze the costs associated with different techniques for remediating contaminated soil, highlighting the challenges faced in cost analysis. The project also reviewed existing methodologies

and available examples and guidelines for ecological risk assessment (ERA). Based on this review, an optimal ERA methodology was selected for the BIOSYSMO project, ensuring the most effective approach for ecological risk assessment in the project's context.

Moreover, five cases of study have been defined for the execution of the LCA/LCC based on the project. In addition, the stabilization solidification (S/S) process has been taken into account as the potential benchmark. Also, the potential functional units have been established. In parallel, two novel environmental impact categories involved in the project ("Biodiversity" and "Ecosystems Services") have been assessed in order to be analyzed its function in BIOSYSMO project. Besides, the LCC protocol and methodology have been defined.

1. BIOSYSMO PROGRESS

CIIMAR

CIIMAR carried out a one-year seasonal sampling campaign at site 4 (Douro River estuary, one location) and site 5 (Lima River estuary, two locations), aiming to quantify target pollution parameters and characterize the microbial community associated to sediments and plant roots. From both sites, sediments (vegetated and non-vegetated) and salt marsh plant species (two species) were sampled, in four different seasons, to quantify the metals content, pharmaceuticals presence and other physicochemical parameters, as well as to characterize the microbial communities in some of the collected samples. With the exception of pharmaceutical analysis, all other analyses are being done by CIIMAR team. Most data are already obtained, being now integrated.

To select microorganisms tolerant to metals and able to degrade pharmaceuticals, enrichment methods were used. Under laboratory-scale conditions, sediments sampled from sites 4 and 5 were exposed to a single or combination of selected contaminants. After the incubation period, the presence of metals and/or pharmaceuticals was quantified to determine their removal rate. Additionally, the enriched cultures were analysed to determine the bacterial group diversity. From enriched cultures, bacteria were isolated, identified and are being tested for their tolerance to metals and/or capacity to degrade pharmaceuticals. Moreover, these microorganisms are being tested also for their plant growth-promoting traits.

UPM

UPM has been working on WP3, Task 3.3 (Genetic engineering of poplar for improved soil phytoremediation). In this time, we have identified two different poplar genotypes that can tolerate an excess of Zn and Cd and that can accumulate them. We have performed metal tolerance assays and metal accumulation quantification in poplar and also RNA-seq studies to identify

candidate genes related to phytoremediation capabilities. The work developed in task T3.3 allowed the identification of two poplar tolerant genotypes for Zn and Cd excess. Moreover, RNA-seq analysis performed in T3.3 allowed the identification of new candidate genes for further genetic modifications to generate more tolerant and metal-accumulative poplar genotypes.

1. BIOSYSMO PROGRESS

AXIA INNOVATION

AXIA INNOVATION

AXIA Innovation is leading Work Package 7, and is focusing on the exploitation activities, mainly related to innovation management and knowledge management. In this regard, the exploitation routes expected by the partners have been defined, which are mainly scientific and market-oriented exploitation.

At the same time, a thorough assessment of the markets linked to BIOSYSMO has been done in a first stage to identify the key markets for the project as well as a SWOT and PESTLE analysis have been carried out to have a clear

understanding of both internal and external environments. AXIA has already collected the background knowledge that the partners bring to the project. Also, the expected foreground knowledge has been analyzed even though foreground knowledge will be continuously updated until the end of the project.

In this line, the list of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and the ownership schemes expected have been identified from the beginning of the project and AXIA will monitor and update them as necessary during the project lifetime.

CNRS

During this period, CNRS significantly contributed to the Work Package 1, Task 1.2 by gathering and compiling the physicochemical characterization of the samples collected on BIOSYSMO sites and the results of the analysis of the pollutants identified, together with the associated analytical protocols. A wide variety of organic and metallic compounds were identified. Soil, sediment, (ground)water or plant samples were analyzed, depending on the sites. The applied methods will be used to quantify the pollutants during the project's future tasks.

CNRS performed a qualitative suspect screening of pesticides in soil samples from site 1 of UBFC in order to determine, for the first time on this site, which pesticides were present on the soils collected under 2 poplar plantations and 2 cultivated soils (current maize and rapeseed). More than 50 different pesticides

were detected in these samples.

CNRS also analyzed samples provided by several partners. Three selected pharmaceuticals and some of their transformation products were quantified in the vegetated and non-vegetated sediment samples from the one-year seasonal sampling campaign at site 4 (Douro River estuary, one location) and site 5 (Lima River estuary, two locations) of CIIMAR's partner. This allowed to follow the contamination by these pharmaceutical compounds on these sites seasonally during one year.

In addition, CNRS carried out a suspect screening of pharmaceutical and pesticides compounds present in the sediment samples collected during the autumn campaign at the two CIIMAR sites. The 20 more often detected compounds were also quantified in the spring campaign samples.

1. BIOSYSMO PROGRESS

TAUW

Within Task 1.1 TAUW has conducted various sampling campaigns in Belgium (sites 6, 11 and 12), Spain (sites 7 and 9) and Germany (site 13) over the last year to provide soil and groundwater samples to different partners including JSI, LEITAT and UBU. The water samples collected are characterized by different types of contaminants including heavy metals and metal(loid)s, volatile and non-volatile petroleum hydrocarbons, BTEX, naphthalene and various types of organochlorides (chlorinated ethenes, chlorinated methanes and hexachlorbutadiene). For soils only samples contaminated with non-volatile petroleum hydrocarbons were collected. The samples should help BIOSYSMO partners to develop multiple remedial approaches, enrich microbial consortia or isolate microorganisms with beneficial traits for contaminant transformation/biodegradation.

At site 7 in Spain TAUW is running an in-situ biosparging measure for elimination of volatile and non-volatile petroleum hydrocarbons, BTEX and naphthalene. Additional samples have been collected from the site to better understand the contribution of microorganisms to the elimination of the hydrocarbons, BTEX and naphthalene and also to identify the

natural metabolic degrading potential present in the aquifer. Finally, samples have been collected from this site to assess how the remedial measures implemented in-situ improve the ecotoxicity of the water treated.

Site 13 was recently added to the BIOSYSMO project. This site is located in Germany and affected by chlorinated ethene contamination.

A biostimulation/bioaugmentation in-situ remedial measure using a groundwater recirculation system will start in Feb-March 2024, which is planned to last for approx. 2 years. In Fall 2023 and at the beginning of 2024 TAUW has coordinated drilling and civil works for installation of infiltration wells and extraction wells and also installation works for a dosing station. The recirculation and dosing system are currently being tested. Time 0 samples have been taken for characterization and also for biodegradation assays using BES technology by LEITAT. During the course of the biostimulation and subsequent bioaugmentation phases additional samples will be gained to better understand microbiological processes in-situ and hopefully provide new communities for BES treatment.

1. BIOSYSMO PROGRESS

EXELISIS

The BIOSYSMO project has undertaken various communication and dissemination activities to promote its goals and outcomes. These activities include the development of communication tools such as posters, leaflets, roll-ups, and brochures, which serve as informative materials about the project.

The BIOSYSMO website and social media accounts on LinkedIn and Twitter are regularly updated to provide up-to-date information and engage with the audience. The project's communication team also monitors statistics related to website visits, social media engagement, and other relevant metrics.

The consortium pays close attention to the communication and dissemination activities performed, including

publications, participation in events, and online communication of BIOSYSMO results. These activities are regularly monitored to ensure effective dissemination of project findings.

Several communication and dissemination activities have been completed, and the project has announced the release of 2 newsletters and 5 press releases, providing updates and insights into the project's progress.

The consortium has also held internal meetings with sister projects like SYMBIOREM and NYMPHE, as well as active projects such as MIBIREM, GREENER, ELECTRA, and EiCLaR. A joint workshop during the BioRemid 2023 conference, was held on June 28, 2023, in Switzerland and an upcoming one is being planned.

1. BIOSYSMO PROGRESS

IMPERIAL COLLEGE
OF LONDON

Imperial College
London

ICL have made progress in the development of microbial strains to biodegrade persistent pollutants of interest identified in WP1. Lindane was highlighted as a particularly abundant compound present in soil and groundwater samples isolated from Site 13. A genetic construct carrying the lindane degradation pathway native to *Sphingobium japonicum* UT26 has been assembled and delivered to the industrially relevant microorganism *Pseudomonas putida* KT2440. Investigations are underway to verify whether the engineered strain is capable of degrading lindane to use as a sole carbon source. Preliminary toxicity tests indicate that lindane does not inhibit growth of the wild-type strain when

an alternative carbon source, such as glucose, is provided. A suite of plasmids (the pMATING series) has been obtained for use in the BIOSYSMO project. These plasmids are capable of transfer between individuals (including Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, and yeast) without the need for an additional helper strain. The self-propagating nature of this plasmid machinery has been demonstrated using an *E. coli* strain carrying the pMATING α -msfGFP plasmid which was successfully delivered to *P. putida* KT2440 in a bi-parental mating protocol. The lindane degradation pathway will be integrated into plasmids from this collection to enable propagation of the pathway within a microbial community.

2. BIOSYSMO OUTCOMES

#1

Apply recent advances in computational and bioinformatics tools to accelerate and improve the design of synergistic biosystems for efficient bioremediation of polluted soil, sediments, and water.

#3

Provide science-based knowledge on the interaction of various contaminant classes within the bioremediation system and the matrix. Conduct a systematic assessment of detoxification potential, introduce new efficient analytical methods, and deliver site-specific risk assessments.

#6

Introduce new approaches for efficient bioremediation and resource recycling.

#2

Implement innovative enhancement strategies, including genetic enhancement, BES, microbial micro aggregation, and immobilization, combined in novel hybrid systems. Explore additional opportunities for resource recycling through developed phytomanagement strategies.

#4

Validate newly developed bioremediation methods in lab conditions using real polluted matrices (TRL 4) within the project timeframe. Selected strategies will undergo field testing and validation (TRL 5).

#7

Design healthy symbiotic relationships between microbial communities and plants to revitalize and restore ecosystems, fostering pollution removal and supporting additional biodiversity.

#5

Apply advanced assessments on Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Life Cycle Costing (LCC), social LCA, and Environmental Risk Assessment (ERA) to diverse technologies and bioremediation scenarios. Adopt FAIR data principles to facilitate data re-use and contribute to the GLAD network.

#8

Develop environmentally-friendly biotechnologies for soil and water recovery, with thorough assessment using LCA methodology and Environmental Risk Assessment.

Optimize metabolic routes and symbiotic relationships to reduce external chemical or energy consumption, minimizing the environmental footprint of bioremediation processes. Conduct (eco)toxicity assessments for solid conclusions on benefits, identify potential secondary toxic metabolites, and employ QSAR models to enhance data availability for Environmental Risk Assessment (ERA).

#9

3. BIOSYSMO PRESENCE AT EVENTS

AQUACONSOIL 2023, 11-15 SEPTEMBER 2023

From September 11th to 15th, 2023, Dr. Rocío Barros and Alberto Soto Cañas actively participated at the Aquaconsoil conference held in Prague. Their presentation centered on the BIOSYSMO Project, delving into pioneering methods for improving the removal of mixed pollutants through collaborative bioremediation systems. Alberto delivered an enlightening speech, revealing the impressive results attained in the phytoremediation of polluted waters.

[Find out more about the event!](#)

RESEARCHERS NIGHT 2023, 29 SEPTEMBER 2023

The BIOSYSMO Project took part in the ResearchersNight 2023, a dynamic event hosted by the National Technical University of Athens, on 29 September 2023! The European Researchers' Night is a Europe-wide public event, which displays the diversity of science and its impact on citizens' daily lives in fun, inspiring ways. During this engaging event, our partner, EXELISIS, played a vital role by interacting with attendees and distributing informative brochures to young researchers and students. The materials provided shed light on the transformative power of bioremediation in addressing environmental pollution challenges.

Under the same initiative, this year, UBU participate to the European Researchers Night, featuring engaging workshops for children. This time, the workshop was focused on microorganisms, exploring their applications in beverage production and their vital role in plant growth. This initiative aligned with sustainability and environmental leadership, showcasing various European projects they are actively contributing to.

3. BIOSYSMO PRESENCE AT EVENTS

CIIMAR'S OPEN DAY, 17 SEPTEMBER 2023

During CIIMAR's Open Day on September 17, 2023, the BIOSYSMO team showcased their passion for environmental restoration. This is a regular event attracting over 20K visitors every year, including kids and families. Visitors of all ages experienced hands-on demonstrations, witnessing how CIIMAR scientists isolate "Decontamination MicroNinjas", primarily bacteria with remarkable remediation capabilities. [Find out more!](#)

11^{as} JORNADAS PORTUGUESAS DE ENGENHARIA COSTEIRA E PORTUÁRIA

During October 3-4 2023, the 11th Portuguese Coastal and Port Engineering Days took place at the Cruise Terminal of the Port of Leixões. CIIMAR participated in this event.

[Find out more!](#)

GREENET BROKERAGE EVENT, 18 OCTOBER 2023

On October 18, 2023, BIOSYSMO participated in the GREENET Brokerage Event for Horizon Europe (HE) Cluster 5 - 2024 calls. During this event, a concise overview of the BIOSYSMO project was presented in face-to-face meetings as part of efforts to engage with research communities.

[Further information about the event can be found HERE!](#)

3. BIOSYSMO PRESENCE AT EVENTS

TREC EXPEDITION, 28-29 OCTOBER 2023

IIMAR engaged in the TREC (Traversing European Coastlines) expedition, conducting a Science Communication activity titled “Decontamination Ninjas” to introduce the BIOSYSMO concept to the public. Researchers from CIIMAR, EMBL, and the Tara Ocean Foundation, along with representatives from the Portuguese scientific community, shared insights into the expedition’s history, outlined its objectives, and expressed anticipation for its outcomes. The public engagement program included diverse activities for schools and the general public. Additionally, a ‘Science on Tour’ event at a local café provided an opportunity for TREC scientists to engage in discussions with the public on scientific topics related to the expedition.

[Find out more](#)

INNOVATION HUB FOR SURFACE AND COLLOID BIOLOGY RESEARCH EVENT, 9-10 NOVEMBER, 2023

On November 9, 2023, JSI organised the “Innovation Hub for Surface and Colloid Biology Research” event, aiming to elevate the prominence of colloid biology, educate a dynamic scientific community, and fortify industry collaborations for addressing practical challenges. Furthermore, a WINTER SCHOOL titled “Exploring microbial cell-surface and cell colloid interactions: advanced analytical methods” took place on September 10th, supported by another EU-funded project, SurfBIO. [For additional details, HERE!](#)

ECOMONDO, 7-10 NOVEMBER, 2023

BIOSYSMO Project is gearing up for Ecomondo 2024, the premier European event for ecological transition and innovative circular economy models! More than 1500 companies attend each year and BIOSYSMO had the chance to attend along with the EU bioremediation cluster of projects. November 7-10, 2023, in Italy BIOSYSMO was presented aiming to engage, share insights, and collaborate for a greener, regenerative future.

[Find out more!](#)

3. BIOSYSMO PRESENCE AT EVENTS

EUROPEAN MISSION SOIL WEEK, 21-23 NOVEMBER, 2023

BIOSYSMO Project participated in the European Mission Soil Week discussions from November 21-23, 2023! Hosted by the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC) in Madrid, Spain. This is a major event that emphasises the importance of soil protection, restoration, and monitoring for sustainable land management. Representatives from Universidad de Burgos and UBFC engaged with fellow cluster projects like MIBIREM, EDAPHOS, GREENER Project H2020, and InBestSoil.

[Check the agenda here!](#)

BIOTECHLIFE 2023, 13 DECEMBER 2023

CIIMAR participated in the “The Importance of Phytoremediation and Bioremediation in Marine Biotechnology” workshop at BiotechLife 2023 at the Escola Superior de Saúde do Porto. The CIIMAR team gave some engaging presentations, making the event a memorable showcase of the promising future offered by Biotechnology.

[For additional details, HERE!](#)

5. BIOSYSMO OFFICIAL VIDEO

We're thrilled to announce the release of the BIOSYSMO project video. Take a look and find out how BIOSYSMO is combining nature's microbial power with a computational model-driven framework for next-level bioremediation solutions.

Watch the video now!

The video was released last October 2023 and was promoted through a LinkedIn sponsored campaign hitting 14,525 impressions. With more than 5,6 k views the BIOSYSMO concept reached a wider audience and spread the word about its biosystems and how they can affect water quality and soil health.

7. CLUSTERING ACTIVITIES

BioBio 2024, June 16-20 June, 2024

BIOSYSMO Project is gearing up for the 7th International Symposium on Biosorption and Biodegradation/Bioremediation – BioBio2024 in Prague. The event is scheduled for June 16-20, 2024. The team is collaborating with the EU Bioremediation cluster, along with SYMBIOREM, MIBIREM, EiCLaR, and Nymphe projects, and is planning to organise a satellite workshop during the BioBio event. Moreover, the BIOSYSMO team is planning to attend the conference with several abstracts. Mark the following dates:

- Abstract submission deadline: Feb. 12, 2024.

- Notification of paper acceptance: Feb. 29, 2024.

- Early registration fee deadline: March 11, 2024.

For more check **HERE!**

European Mission Soil Week, 21-23 November, 2023

Our cluster project MIBIREM shared a blog article on Mission Soil Week. During the event our partners UBU and UBFC met up with the representatives from several projects including PREPSOIL, InBestSoil, Loess, ISLANDR, Solo, and EDAPHOS. Thanks to Mrs Ana Babic for composing this interesting article and to the BIOSYSMO team for disseminating our work. Find out more: **HERE!**

EUCircularTalk, 12 September 2023

On September 12th, 2023, the European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform, INNOWO, BIOSYSMO, SYMBIOREM, Electra, MIBIREM, Nymphe, and GREENER Projects collaborated to organize the EUCircularTalks: Bioremediation as an effective tool for a clean environment. BIOSYSMO project was presented by Prof Blanca Velasco Arroyo, while our project coordinator Dr. Lila Otero participated in the round table discussions during the Q&A session. Thanks to Dr Agnieszka Szyk for this excellent initiative.

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WWW.BIOSYSMO.EU | INFO@BIOSYSMO.EU

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